

Sensory reconstruction of the fossil lorid *Mioeuoticus*: systematic and evolutionary implications

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Abstract

The evolutionary history of lorises and pottos (family Lorisidae) potentially dates back to the late Oligocene of Namibia, but a later moderate diversification of this family occurred during the Miocene of Africa and Asia. In the African Miocene, the family Lorisidae is represented solely by one genus: *Mioeuoticus*. The phyletic position of *Mioeuoticus* has been a source of debate, as it has been suggested to belong to either the stem of the family Lorisidae or to be further nested within lorids, as a sister to the African potto clade (subfamily Perodicticinae). Reconstructing the internal sensory anatomy of this specimen could shed some light on this debate and also possibly clarify how modern lorid olfactory and visual sensitivity and locomotor abilities evolved. Here, we collected data from the nasal turbinals, bony labyrinths and orbits of *Mioeuoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052), from the early Miocene of Rusinga Island, Kenya. These results are consistent with *Mioeuoticus* having developed typical modern lorid behaviour (i.e. slow locomotion, nocturnal activity pattern) and olfactory abilities consistent with modern representatives. However, the arrangement of the nasal turbinals showing an intermediate state between lemuroids and lorids is more consistent with a basal position of *Mioeuoticus* within the family Lorisidae or even the superfamily Lorioidea.

Keywords: *lorid; sensory; phylogeny; Miocene; primate; Mioeuoticus*

1. Introduction

Lorises and pottos (family Lorisidae) are nocturnal strepsirrhine primates that live in tropical, central Africa, and southern and southeastern Asia. Lorids are the result of a relatively poor Miocene primate radiation (López-Torres & Silcox, 2020), which became highly specialized in a nocturnal, arboreal lifestyle and insectivorous dietary behaviours, often showing adaptations for gum extraction (Burrows et al., 2020; Nekaris and Bearder, 2007; Nekaris et al., 2010). There has been substantial research dedicated to the ecology, behaviours and evolutionary relationships of the modern Lorids, but this stands in stark contrast to analyses of their fossil relatives. Major aspects of lorid phylogeny, systematics, reconstructed behaviour, and functional anatomy remain unresolved, mainly because these primates are exceptionally rare in the fossil record.

In recent decades, however, our understanding of early loriform evolution has improved considerably due to new fossil discoveries and ongoing molecular studies on extant relatives (e.g., Flynn & Morgan, 2005; Harrison, 2010, 2011; Kunitatsu et al., 2017; Simon et al. 1995; Shoshani et al. 1996; Philips & Walker, 2000; Pickford, 2015; Pickford et al., 2006; Masters et al. 2005; McCrossin, 1992; Mein & Ginsburg, 1997; Seiffert, 2007; Rasmussen & Nekaris, 1998). These data clarify the

41 interrelationships of extant lorid genera, double the temporal range of crown loriforms and reveal
42 seemingly good convergence between fossils and molecular divergence date estimates in certain
43 parts of the phylogenetic tree (López-Torres & Silcox, 2020). The available fossil evidence has
44 significantly advanced our knowledge of loroid evolutionary history, such as the potential origins of
45 loroids (Seiffert et al., 2003) and lorids (Pickford, 2015), certain aspects of their locomotor ecology
46 (Walker et al., 2008), as well as a greater diversity of dietary behaviours in extinct forms (Fulwood et
47 al., 2021; López-Torres et al., 2020; MacPhee & Jacobs, 1986; Selig et al., 2024a,b).

48 Despite these advances, many questions remain as to the reconstructed behaviour in fossil lorid
49 forms. Whereas most fossil lorid material is comprised of dentognathic or, occasionally, postcranial
50 material (Harrison, 2010; López-Torres & Silcox, 2020), an almost complete cranium is known from
51 the early Miocene of Rusinga Island, Kenya, belonging to *Mioeuoticus shipmani* (Philips & Walker,
52 2000). The phylogenetic position of *M. shipmani* is currently uncertain, with Walker et al. (2008)
53 placing it as sister group to all African lorids (i.e. subfamily Perodicticinae), while Harrison (2010)
54 argued that the genus *Mioeuoticus* belongs to a more basal lineage at the stem of lorids. In either
55 case, *Mioeuoticus* represents an early member of the family Loridae and understanding its
56 behaviour provides a deep evolutionary perspective in the context of the clade. The reconstructed
57 behaviour of *M. shipmani* remains largely unexplored, but it is not completely unknown. Walker et
58 al. (2008) found that the semicircular canals (SCCs) in *M. shipmani* had a similar relative size to those
59 seen in modern slow lorises (genus *Nycticebus*). The SCCs provide information on the body's position
60 in space, contributing in particular to the stabilization of gaze in locomotion (Spoor et al., 2007).
61 Among modern primates, slower-moving species tend to have smaller SCCs for a given body mass
62 compared to faster-moving taxa. The similarities between *Mioeuoticus* and *Nycticebus* found by
63 Walker et al. (2008) suggest, therefore, that *Mioeuoticus* was most likely a slow-moving arboreal
64 quadruped, in a similar fashion to modern-day lorids. However, besides the reconstructed
65 locomotor behaviour, nothing is known about other aspects of its behaviour and, in particular, its
66 sensory capabilities.

67 The main aim of this project is to deduce the sensory capacities of the early Miocene lorid
68 *Mioeuoticus*. The relative timing of the evolution of these characteristics may have important
69 implications for the phyletic position of the early Miocene lorid *Mioeuoticus*.

70 *Vision*

71 Vision draws instantaneous environmental information to deduce how to interact and adapt with
72 various life-preserving factors, including predators, food and long-distance conspecific
73 communication, providing mammals with distal sensory control (e.g., Crompton, 1995; Dominy et al.
74 2004; Bearder et al. 2006). The visual system is comprised of the cornea, pupil, lens and retina (Grey,
75 1878). Light that passes into the eye is refracted by the cornea, and adjustably controlled and
76 focussed into the retina by the pupil and lens. When light reaches the retina, photoreceptors convert
77 the stimuli to electrochemical signals which travel along the optic nerve to the brain for processing
78 and behavioural response (Baker, 2012).

79 The dimensions of the intra-orbital surface can be directly related to the size of the optic nerve in
80 primates (Kremers, 2005). Direct comparisons with optic nerve measurements in extant primates
81 with known visual capacities can provide a basis to hypothesise the visual acuity of fossil primates
82 (Kirk & Kay, 2004). The left intra-orbital surface of the *Mioeuoticus* cranium volume rendering has
83 been significantly taphonomically distorted, but the right intra-orbital surface appears to be well
84 preserved with little to no apparent damage.

85 *Olfaction*

86 To ensure survival, mammals rely strongly on their sense of smell to convey critical information about
 87 food seeking, mate selection, hazard detection and behavioural immune responses (e.g., Nekaris
 88 2005; Barton, 2006; Brennan & Kendrick, 2006; Sanchez-Andrade & Kendrick, 2009; Hoover, 2010;
 89 Nevo & Heymann, 2015; Schwambergová, 2023). The olfactory system is structured as long, scrolled,
 90 spongy networks of bone within the nasal cavity, known as turbinals, turbinates or conchae. The
 91 turbinals are lined with a specialised tissue called olfactory epithelium, which is used to interpret
 92 smell (Smith et al. 2004, 2007a). Thousands of chemically diverse odour molecules and pheromones
 93 are detected and recognised by the olfactory system, which is converted into an electrical signal sent
 94 to the brain for interpretation and behavioural response (Smith et al. 2007b; Laska & Salazar, 2015).

95 The proportions, number and complexity of these structures give strong evidence of the olfactory
 96 landscape, behavioural ecology and phylogenetic affinities of fossil primates (e.g., Smith et al. 2006,
 97 2014; Lundeen & Kirk, 2009; Maier & Ruf, 2014). These data may detect a system specialised to a
 98 specific range of odorants, which can give a strong indication as to the primate trends in the
 99 evolution of nasal morphometry and airflow (Lundeen, 2017; Lundeen & Kirk, 2019; Lundeen, 2020;
 100 Lundeen & Kay, 2022). Turbinals are delicate and rarely preserved in fossil specimens, limiting
 101 opportunities to make direct observations of the olfactory periphery in extinct primates. Fortunately,
 102 the turbinals of the *Mioeuoticus* specimen in this study are preserved with minimal damage or
 103 distortion.

104 *Audition*

105 Mammals depend on audition for vital interactions with their environments, including food detection
 106 and attainment (e.g. Dittus, 1984; Goerlitz & Siemers, 2007), hazard detection and evasion (e.g.,
 107 Blumstein, 2002; Zuberbühler, 2007), stabilising balance (e.g., Spoor et al. 2007), and participating in
 108 communal exchanges governing territoriality or mating (Semple & McComb, 2000; Ramsier et al.
 109 2012). The auditory system is comprised of two main structures; fluid-filled receptor organs form the
 110 membranous labyrinth, which is suspended within the petrous temporal bone inside a network of
 111 bony voids known as the bony labyrinth (Purves et al. 2008; Ekdale, 2016). The bony labyrinth
 112 consists of semicircular canals (SCCs), the utricle and the sacculus, and the cochlea. As sound waves
 113 enter the inner ear, the fluid in the receptor organs undulates and disturbs microscopic hairs that
 114 convert the sound or movement signals to electrical signals and send them to the brain for
 115 interpretation and behavioural response (Walker et al. 2008; Kirk & Gosselin-Ildari, 2009).

116 The orientation, relative position, and size of the semi-circular canals give strong evidence of the
 117 visual acuity, locomotor behaviour and phylogenetic affinities of fossil primates (e.g., Spoor, 1994,
 118 1995, 1996; Jeffery et al. 2008). Measurements of semicircular canals in extant mammals with known
 119 locomotor behaviours can provide a basis for direct comparisons with which to test hypotheses
 120 about locomotion in fossil primates (e.g., Spoor, 2003, 2007; Rook et al., 2004; Silcox et al., 2009;
 121 Gonzales et al. 2019). The bony labyrinths of the *Mioeuoticus* specimen in this study are difficult to
 122 determine due to poor CT resolution, but some diagnostic structures appear to be preserved with
 123 minimal damage or distortion.

124

125 *Phylogenetic Implications*

126 These data may provide critical insights as to whether *Mioeuoticus* are stem or crown members of
 127 Lorissidae, or possibly advanced stem, or very basal crown, lorisiforms. To better understand the

128 phylogenetic and ecological significance of these observations for *Mioeuoticus*, we provide a
 129 comparative framework with analyses of extant and extinct specimens in associated literature for
 130 evaluating sensory character evolution to assess the relationships between fossil and living lorises.
 131 Understanding how fossil lorises relate to their living relatives is critical for explaining major trends
 132 in primate evolution. A better understanding of the relationships among extinct and extant lorises
 133 may speak to the question of the biogeographic origin of this primate family and a broader
 134 understanding of the characteristic low diversity of modern lorises.

135

136 *Institutional abbreviations*

137 BAA—Department of Evolutionary Anthropology, Duke University, Durham, NC, USA; MCZ—Museum
 138 of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA, USA; KNM-RU—National Museums of
 139 Kenya, Rusinga Island collection, Nairobi, Kenya.

140

141 **2. Methods**

142 The cranium of *Mioeuoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052; housed in the Palaeontological Collections of
 143 the National Museums of Kenya, Nairobi), had been previously scanned on-site using a portable
 144 micro-CT scanner by a team of Kyoto University. The resulting scan has 575 total slices, providing a
 145 16-bit TIFF image stack data sets for the cranium which were rendered as 3D volumes in Avizo 3D
 146 (Visualization Sciences Group, Berlin). The internal anatomy of the sensory systems was
 147 reconstructed as digital endocasts from this three-dimensional rendering. These structures of
 148 *Mioeuoticus* were manually segmented in each slice using the brush tool. These data are used to
 149 reconstruct the complex sensory system of the *Mioeuoticus* specimen, which may provide critical
 150 evidence on the phylogenetic affinities of this taxon. Unfortunately, the only available scan of the
 151 entire cranium has poor resolution, and some structures are not distinguishable from the
 152 background artefacts.

153 *Vision*

154 The visual acuity of *Mioeuoticus shipmani* is hypothesised following the Optic Foramen Quotient
 155 (OFQ) method by Kirk & Kay, 2004. The length and width of the orbital and optic foramen cavities in
 156 the three-dimensional volume rendering of the *Mioeuoticus* cranium are taken using the ruler tool
 157 on Avizo 3D. The formula for the area of an orbital cavity is then calculated as follows: $A = \pi \cdot a \cdot b$;
 158 where A is the area of the orbital cavity, a is the major radius length and b is the minor radius length
 159 of the optic foramen and orbital cavity. We then measured the prosthion-inion (P-I) length, which
 160 runs from the craniometric point, which is the most anterior point in the midline on the alveolar
 161 process of the maxilla, to the tip of the external occipital protuberance. This calculation is used as a
 162 substitute and accurate estimation for the total body size of this specimen.

163 These data are then added as variables into the equation by Kirk & Kay (2004) to approximate optic
 164 foramen size relative to eye size, as follows;

$$165 \quad (\text{Optic Foramen Area}/\text{Orbit Area}) * 100 = \text{Optic Foramen Index (OFI)}$$

166 Kay & Kirk (2004) state that this equation increasingly overestimates eye size as the body size of a
 167 specimen increases, and thus to remove this bias, the OFI result for body size must be adjusted using
 168 the equation;

169 $OFQ = (Observed\ OFI - Expected\ OFI) / Expected\ OFI * 100.$

170 The expected OFI is calculated with two empirical regression formulas to express the OFI as a
 171 percentage of that which is expected for diurnal anthropoids ($LnOFI = 3.39983 - 0.56624 * \ln [P-I$
 172 $length]$) and nocturnal strepsirrhines ($LnOFI = 2.46913 - 0.58138 * \ln [P-I\ length]$) of similar P-I length.
 173 Therefore, we input the P-I length of the *Mioeuticus* holotype into both of these equations and raise
 174 the result of these calculations to the power of e, where $e \approx 2.718$, to determine the diurnal
 175 anthropoid regression (daOFQ) and nocturnal strepsirrhine regression (nsOFQ) for the specimen, as
 176 follows;

177

178 Diurnal Anthropoid Expected OFI: $LnOFI = 3.39983 - 0.56624 * \ln (P-I\ length)$

179 $daOFQ = (Observed\ OFI - Expected\ OFI) / Expected\ OFI * 100$

180

181 Nocturnal strepsirrhine Expected OFI: $LnOFI = 2.46913 - 0.58138 * \ln (P-I\ length)$

182 $nsOFQ = (Observed\ OFI - Expected\ OFI) / Expected\ OFI * 100$

183

184 These data were then directly compared to the daOFQ and nsOFQ of extant specimens determined
 185 in Kay & Kirk (2004: table 5) to produce an assessment of visual acuity in *Mioeuticus*.

186 *Olfaction*

187 We provide a detailed description of the reconstructed *Mioeuticus* olfactory turbinals, in which all
 188 nomenclature and definitions of turbinals follow Smith and Rossie (2008). All turbinals are described
 189 in an anterior-to-posterior sequence as they appear in coronal view. We follow the convention of
 190 numbering ethmoturbinals using Roman numerals from anterior to posterior view. All descriptions of
 191 turbinal morphology follow an anterior-to-posterior sequence based on successive coronal CT slices.
 192 Terms used to describe turbinal shape in coronal cross-section follow Lundeen & Kirk (2019). When
 193 possible, turbinals were segmented from the lateral wall of the nasal fossa at the point where the
 194 turbinal's basal lamina contacts the lateral wall. We also quantify the surface areas of both the
 195 olfactory turbinals and the maxilloturbinals of the *Mioeuticus* specimen using the surface area tool
 196 in Avizo. These data are correlated with turbinal surface areas of a range of extant strepsirrhines and
 197 haplorhines calculated by Lundeen & Kirk (2009) to hypothesise the olfactory abilities of *Mioeuticus*
 198 compared to other similarly sized primates.

199 *Audition*

200 We provide detailed descriptions of the overall morphology of the bony labyrinth, focused mainly on
 201 the orientation, relative position and size of the semi-circular canals. The anterior, posterior and
 202 lateral semi-circular canals are described, respectively, as they appear in anterior-to-posterior view
 203 based on successive coronal CT slices. We are also able to measure the angles between the
 204 semicircular canals. The angle between the three canal arcs is measured at the greatest width of the
 205 anterior and posterior semicircular canals on the transverse plane, following Spoor and Zonneveld
 206 (1998).

207 Additionally, we measure the common crus length (CCL). The medial end of the anterior (superior)
 208 semicircular canal joins with the upper part of the posterior canal to form a bony limb, known as the
 209 common crus (Lebrun et al. 2010; Perier et al. 2016). CCL is measured from the opening of the
 210 vestibular aqueduct in the vestibular wall to the bifurcation point of the common crus – known as
 211 the crus commune apex – following inner ear morphological landmark locations defined in Lebrun et
 212 al. (2010). The length of the common crus in the reconstructed *Mioeoticus* inner ear is compared to
 213 the mean CCL in extant slow- and fast-moving primates (Perier et al. 2016: table 4).

214

215 3. Results

216 The cranial measurements of the holotype of *Mioeoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052) are as follows;
 217 total length of 61.8mm, cranial height of 26.3mm neurocranial width of 33.9mm and maxillary width
 218 of 30.5mm.

219 Vision

220 Following the OFI and OFQ equations of Kay & Kirk (2004), the daOFQ and nsOFQ calculated for the
 221 holotype of *Mioeoticus shipmani* are as follows:

$$222 \quad \text{Optic Foramen Index (OFI)} = (\text{Optic Foramen Area}/\text{Orbit Area}) * 100$$

$$223 \quad (2.73/214.3) * 100 = 1.273915072$$

$$224 \quad \text{Diurnal Anthropoid Expected OFI: } \ln\text{OFI} = 3.39983 - 0.56624 * \ln(\text{P-I length})$$

$$225 \quad 60.33 = \text{P-I length of } \textit{Mioeoticus}$$

$$226 \quad \ln(6.033) = 4.099829492$$

$$227 \quad \ln\text{OFI} = 3.39983 - 0.56624 * 4.099829492 = 1.078342548$$

$$228 \quad \text{Expected OFI} = e^{1.078342548} = 2.939802929$$

$$229 \quad (\text{da})\text{OFQ} = (\text{Observed OFI} - \text{Expected OFI}) / \text{Expected OFI} * 100$$

$$230 \quad \text{daOFQ} = ((1.273915072 - 2.939802929) / 2.939802929) * 100$$

$$231 \quad \text{daOFQ} = -56.6666507$$

232

$$233 \quad \text{Nocturnal strepsirrhine Expected OFI: } \ln\text{OFI} = 2.46913 - 0.58138 * \ln(\text{P-I Length})$$

$$234 \quad 60.33 = \text{P-I length of } \textit{Mioeoticus}$$

$$235 \quad \ln(6.033) = 4.099829492$$

$$236 \quad \text{Expected OFI} = e^{0.085899116} = 1.08969639$$

$$237 \quad \text{nsOFQ} = (\text{Observed OFI} - \text{Expected OFI}) / \text{Expected OFI} * 100$$

238
$$\text{nsOFQ} = ((1.273915072 - 1.08969639) / 1.08969639) * 100$$

239
$$\text{nsOFQ} = 16.90550541$$

240 *Olfaction*

241 Detailed morphological analyses and anatomical measurements for the individual turbinals in the
242 *Mioeuticus* olfactory reconstruction are presented below. These data are likely an underestimation
243 due to the fragmentation and breakage of the turbinals, though still provide a novel physiological
244 understanding of this previously unstudied olfactory system. The internal turbinal measurements are
245 available in Table 1.

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	Left nasoturbinal	Right nasoturbinal	Left frontoturbinal	Right frontoturbinal	Left interturbinal	Right interturbinal	Left ethmoturbinal I	Right ethmoturbinal I	Left ethmoturbinal II	Right ethmoturbinal II	Left ethmoturbinal III	Right ethmoturbinal III	Left nasosacral canal	Right nasosacral canal	Left maxilloturbinal	Right maxilloturbinal
Medial length	8.79	8.58	5.52	5.16	3.62	3.62	8.97	8.85	5.64	5.64	4.41	4.41	3.84	3.84	17.51	18.02
Lateral length	8.05	7.88	6.09	5.39	3.62	3.62	8.69	8.85	10.29	10.29	6.91	6.91	3.84	3.84	17.51	18.02
Anterior width	4.72	3.12	3.93	3.69	0.16	0.16	1.45	1.07	5.67	5.67	6.59	6.59	4.7	4.7	/	/
Posterior width	3.59	3.93	2.3	3.77	0.16	0.16	11.26	3.54	4.41	4.41	6.61	6.61	4.7	4.7	/	/
Scrolled portion	7.81	7.81	/	/	/	/	3.45	2.46	1.28	1.28	1.82	1.82	/	/	1.08	/
Scroll maximum diameter	3.32	2.57	/	/	/	/	2.4	2.57	3.7	3.7	4.94	4.94	/	/	3.5	/
Anterior height	3.87	2.75	5.73	4.84	1.28	1.28	9.1	3.12	2.95	2.95	6.52	6.52	/	/	/	/
Posterior height	12.13	12.57	1.29	1.74	0.05	0.05	2.74	1.48	2.76	2.76	2.57	2.57	/	/	/	/
Bulla portion	/	/	/	/	/	/	0.27	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	2.7	/
Bulla cross-section	/	/	/	/	/	/	2.4	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	3.5	/
Anterior lateral contacts	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	2.35	2.35	6.52	6.52	/	/	/	/
Posterior lateral contacts	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	1.63	1.63	1.73	1.73	/	/	/	/

Table 1. Anatomical measurements of turbinals in the left and right nasal fossae of the holotype of *Mioeoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052). All measurements are in mm. Lateral contacts are measured at the greatest degree of separation from superior and inferior contacts with the nasal fossae wall.

251 The following turbinal morphologies are described sequentially from anterior to posterior on a
 252 coronal plane (reference Figures 1 & 2). The cross-sectional morphology of each of the turbinals is
 253 described below, including details as to the anatomy of the olfactory cavity, the relative position of
 254 each turbinal in the nasal fossa, and the nature of the turbinals' contact with the fossa wall or other
 255 turbinals. It is recognised that debate still lies in whether to group the two closely associated
 256 anterior-most turbinal structures as a single ethmoturbinal (ethmoturbinal I) or divide them into two
 257 ethmoturbinals (ethmoturbinal I and II). Here, we form a conservative approach and divide these
 258 structures into two ethmoturbinals as, in doing so, we form a comprehensive description of each
 259 structural subdivision that may better contribute to future evaluations of these characteristics within
 260 the appropriate comparative context (reference Figure 3). Turbinal names are abbreviated as follows
 261 (left nasal turbinals – uppercase abbreviations, right nasal turbinals – lowercase abbreviations); NT/nt
 262 - nasoturbinals, FT/ft - frontoturbinals, ET/et I-III – ethmoturbinals 1 to 3, IT/it – interturbinals,
 263 MT/mt – maxilloturbinals.

264 The left and right turbinals are separated in the anterior portion of the olfactory cavity by the nasal
 265 septum. In the posterior of the olfactory cavity, a transverse septum separates a superior olfactory
 266 recess from an inferior nasopharyngeal meatus enclosing ET/et II and III, and MT/mt; which remain
 267 separated by the cribriform plate.

268 The left nasal fossa contains one NT, one FT, three ETs, one IT and one MT. The left nasal turbinals are
 269 well preserved overall, with all major turbinals mostly intact. There is a minor mediolateral distortion
 270 of the NT, and ET I, II and III.

271 *Maxilloturbinal (MT)* – This turbinal is the most anterior of the assemblage, situated only 1.3mm
 272 posterior to the piriform aperture, with a slight posterior sloping gradient on the sagittal plane. The
 273 anterior and inferior margins of this turbinal are preserved along the full length of the structure. This
 274 is a double-scrolled turbinal, with both the medially and laterally directed scrolls well preserved. It is
 275 difficult to assess whether the anterolateral wall of the turbinal ceases at the scrolled portion of the
 276 structure - as apparent in the CT rendering - or has been destroyed and would extend to the full
 277 extent of the basal lamina.

278 *Nasoturbinal (NT)* – This turbinal is a single-scrolled structure – that appears almost perfectly
 279 preserved. There is no apparent deformation, fragmentation or destruction. The turbinal is
 280 orientated anteromedially in the olfactory cavity with a significant anteriorly sloping gradient,
 281 15.4mm posterior to the piriform aperture. The anterior-most margin of the turbinal is anterolateral
 282 to the scrolled midsection, which has a 'teardrop' shape in cross-section. The turbinal has a single
 283 direct contact with the superior fossa wall running anteroposteriorly.

284 *Ethmoturbinal I (ET-I)* - This turbinal is in an inferior position to the NT and FT positioned 13.4mm to
 285 the piriform aperture, with a steep anterior gradient on the sagittal plane. It is on the same sagittal
 286 plane as the NT, and inferolateral to the FT. Anteriorly, the ET forms a single bulla for the main
 287 portion of the turbinal, which detaches laterally and arcs into a scroll that reduces to a branching
 288 structure. This enclosed bulla decreases in volume posteriorly. Initially, the enclosed bulla has two
 289 points of contact with the lateral fossa wall. As the bulla detaches to a scroll structure, these
 290 connections merge into a singular contact.

291 *Ethmoturbinal II (ET-II)* – This turbinal is inferomedial to ET-I, situated 13.1mm posterior to the
 292 piriform aperture, and orientated anteromedially in the olfactory cavity with a steep anterior
 293 gradient on the sagittal plane. Anteriorly, the turbinal is a branching structure contacting the superior
 294 and lateral fossa wall. The connection with the superior fossa wall is lost towards the main portion of

295 this turbinal: a singular bulla that terminates at two contacts with the inferior medial and lateral
 296 border of ET-I. The medial contact with ET-I disconnects posteriorly, forming an arcuate structure that
 297 extends horizontally across the nasal fossa and then curves upward to run parallel with the cribriform
 298 plate. It is unclear whether the most posterior margin of the bulla is incomplete, or the resolution of
 299 the scan is too poor to discern it.

300 *Frontoturbinal (FT)* – This turbinal is located inferolateral to the ET-II, orientated anteromedially in
 301 the olfactory cavity with a steep anterior gradient on the sagittal plane. Situated 16.4mm posterior to
 302 the piriform aperture, it has an arcuate morphology; a regular arc that increases in circumference
 303 from anterior to posterior. It cannot be determined whether this is due to damage and
 304 fragmentation of a scroll or if this is the original structure. The turbinal has a single direct contact
 305 with the lateral fossa wall running antero posteriorly.

306 *Ethmoturbinal III (ET-III)* – Anteriorly, this turbinal is inferior to ET-II, located on the same sagittal
 307 plane in the anterior 13.1mm posterior to the piriform aperture. Posteriorly, the turbinal is
 308 inferolateral to ET-II as it is orientated anteromedially in the olfactory cavity with a steep anterior
 309 gradient on the sagittal plane. It is difficult to discern whether this turbinal is bullar (via a superior
 310 and inferior contact with the lateral fossa wall) or arched (with a single contact with the fossa wall),
 311 as part of ET-III is not visible on the CT rendering. Posteriorly, this arch curves more steeply to form a
 312 single medial scroll with branches that contact the lateral and cribriform walls. Finally, a superior
 313 branching contact is also formed. The scroll gradually becomes less pronounced, and the medial
 314 branch extends until the turbinal becomes a single superior branching contact that descends the
 315 centre of the nasal fossa and splits to form two equal curved branches contacting the lateral and
 316 medial fossa walls.

317 *Interturbinal (IT)* - This turbinal is the most posterior of the assemblage, located inferolateral to the
 318 FT, with a gradual anterior gradient on the sagittal plane. It is located 19.6mm posterior to the
 319 piriform aperture, with an arcuate branching structure that projects from the lateral fossa wall
 320 between ethmoturbinal I and II. This turbinal arches broadly, mirroring the curvature of the
 321 anterolateral border of ET-I.

322 The right nasal fossa contains one nt, one ft, three et, one it and one mt. The right nasal turbinals are
 323 well preserved overall, with all major turbinals mostly intact. There is a minor mediolateral distortion
 324 of ET I, II and III.

325 *Maxilloturbinal (mt)* – The structure of this turbinal closely mirrors that of the paired MT in structure
 326 and position, located 0.7mm posterior to the piriform aperture. The basal margins are once again
 327 mostly preserved along the turbinals full length, though the anterior margin is comminuted – as are
 328 the medially and laterally directed scrolls. The laterally directed scroll has begun to degrade to
 329 floating fragments.

330 *Nasoturbinal (nt)* – This turbinal closely matches the structure and position of the paired NT and is
 331 also well preserved, other than anterior deformation of the laterally directed scroll along the coronal
 332 plane. The turbinal is located 15.6mm posterior to the piriform aperture.

333 *Ethmoturbinal I (et-I)* – The ET-I and et-I are similar, though the bulla of et-I does not detach to form a
 334 scroll which then reduces to a branching structure; instead, it detaches immediately from a bulla to
 335 branching morphology from anterior to posterior. The turbinal is positioned 12.2mm from the
 336 piriform aperture. Furthermore, the bulla is much narrower in cross-section and more elliptical than
 337 in ET-I.

338 *Ethmoturbinal II (et-II)* – This turbinal shares the same general arrangement as ET-II and is positioned
339 similarly 14.1mm from the piriform aperture. There is a greater extent of the turbinals that are not
340 evident in the right nasal fossae, either due to damage or poor CT resolution. The ET-II and et-II are
341 almost identical anteriorly, as a branching structure contacting the superior and lateral fossa wall.
342 However, the two contacts of the et-II bulla with the inferior lateral border of ET-I are more lateral
343 and superior, respectively. The bulla is also much more convex posteriorly.

344 *Frontoturbinal (ft)* – Similarly to FT, it has an arcuate morphology; a regular arc that increases in
345 circumference antero posteriorly. The arch is more convex, however, which may be a natural
346 disparity or possibly due to mediodorsal compression and deformation. This turbinal is slightly more
347 posterior than its counterpart, 18.4mm from the piriform aperture.

348 *Ethmoturbinal III (et-III)* – This turbinal is almost identical to ET-III, other than that a greater portion
349 of the arrangement is not evident in the scan, either due to damage or poor CT resolution. Due to
350 this, there is no point at which the scroll of this turbinal can be confirmed to form a fully enclosed
351 bulla as none of the contact points with et-I or the intermediate curvature between these contacts
352 are not visible. It is similarly located to its opposing paired turbinal, 12mm posterior to the piriform
353 aperture.

354 *Interturbinal (it)* – This turbinal is almost completely identical to its right pair, though the anterior
355 segment which extends anteromedially is slightly shorter. The positioning is almost identical too;
356 18.6mm posterior to the piriform aperture. It is difficult to distinguish whether this is a natural
357 variation or due to some minor destruction of the turbinal.

358 Numerous floating fragments are evident in both anterior nasal fossae. Due to severe taphonomic
359 alterations, there is little evidence that can be derived from these fragments, and it cannot be
360 determined which of the turbinals they originate from.

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Figure 1. CT scans through the nasal fossa of the holotype of *Mioeoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052). A-H) slices along the coronal plane showing preservation of left and right nasal fossae: slice number 97 (A), 137 (B), 139 (C), 146 (D), 156 (E), 173 (F), 179 (G) and 190 (H) of 449 total slices. I) Digitally bisected volume renderings of the cranium showing posterior nasal fossa anatomy in *Mioeoticus*. Frag = unidentified floating turbinal fragment. Scale bar is 10mm.

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Figure 2. Three-dimensional volume rendering of the cranium of *Mioeoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052; holotype). Nasal turbinals have been reconstructed. Scale bar is 10mm.

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Figure 3. Turbinals of the holotype of *Mioeoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052) in A) right lateral view; B) medial view of right nasal fossa turbinals; C) left lateral view; D) medial view of left nasal fossa turbinals; and (E) anterior (F), posterior (G), superior (H), and inferior (I) views of all turbinals. Right (uppercase abbreviations) and left (lowercase abbreviations) sides in surface view can be compared with cross-section views in Figure 1. Frag = unidentified floating turbinal fragment. Scale bar is 10mm.

374 The total surface area of the *Mioeuoticus* specimen's reconstructed olfactory assemblage is
 375 1109.92mm², though it is likely that this is an underestimation as breakage and fragmentation are
 376 evident in every turbinal structure. A further estimate of total surface area which may be more
 377 representative is deduced by considering only the most complete turbinal from each pair and
 378 multiplying these data by two. The result of which is 1184mm². The surface areas of the individual
 379 olfactory components are summarised in Table 2. The maxilloturbinals, determined from the average
 380 of each paired olfactory component, comprise the most substantial portion (26%) of the total surface
 381 area. This is followed by ethmoturbinals I (21%) and nasoturbinals (15%), ethmoturbinals II (18%),
 382 ethmoturbinals III (11%), frontoturbinals (6%), the remaining floating fragments (4%) and finally the
 383 interturbinals (2%).

384

<i>Turbinal</i>	<i>Surface area</i>
Maxilloturbinal (left)	151.36
Maxilloturbinal (right)	134.52
Nasoturbinal (left)	77.07
Nasoturbinal (right)	83.38
Ethmoturbinal I (left)	111.13
Ethmoturbinal I (right)	119.18
Frontoturbinal (left)	35.68
Frontoturbinal (right)	31.06
Ethmoturbinal II (left)	111.72
Ethmoturbinal II (right)	84.89
Interturbinal (left)	6.21
Interturbinal (right)	7.36
Ethmoturbinal III (left)	65.58
Ethmoturbinal III (right)	55.95
Fragments (left)	17.74
Fragments (right)	17.09
<i>Total</i>	1109.92

385

386 *Table 2. The total surface area of individual turbinal reconstructions and the overall turbinal assemblage of the holotype of Mioeuoticus*
 387 *shipmani (KNM-RU 2052). Measurements are taken in mm².*

388 *Audition*

389 The general morphology of the cochlea is evident, but distinct structures cannot be discerned. The
 390 linear length of the cochlear canals can be measured at 3.94mm (left) and 4.02mm (right). Three oval
 391 semicircular canals (SCCs) are apparent in both bony labyrinths: the anterior semicircular canal (ASC),
 392 the posterior semicircular canal (PSC), and the lateral semicircular canal (LSC) (Figure 4).

393

394 Figure 4) Reconstructed left (pink) and right (yellow) bony labyrinths of the holotype of *Mioeuticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052) in posterior
 395 view of the cranium. Scale bar is 5mm.

396

397 None of the canal reconstructions are complete, though this is unclear whether this is due to
 398 breakage or scan resolution (Figure 5). The angles between all of the canals are far from orthogonal,
 399 with a large average deviation from orthogonality of 12.7° (Table 3).

400

	<i>LSC-ASC</i>	<i>LSC-PSC</i>	<i>ASC-PSC</i>
<i>Left inner ear</i>	101	101	105
<i>Right inner ear</i>	102	102	105
<i>Deviation from orthogonality</i>	11.5	11.5	15

401

402 Table 3. The angle between the arcs at the greatest width of the anterior, posterior and lateral semicircular canals on the transverse plane
 403 of the holotype of *Mioeuticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052). Abbreviations: LSC – Lateral Semicircular Canal, ASC – Anterior Semicircular
 404 Canal, PSC – Posterior Semicircular Canal. Measurements in degrees.

405 The ASCs and PSCs have a degree of torsion, whereas the LSCs are fairly planar. The ASCs have the
 406 greatest degree of torsion, with the dorsal edge bent significantly forward. The ASC has the largest
 407 radius, and the LSC has the shortest radius of the SCCs. The posterior limb of the LSC with the
 408 ampullar limb of the PSC fuse to form a secondary common crus orthogonal to the plane of the LSC
 409 length. The left LSC is 1.79mm and the right LSC is 1.56mm in length.

410

411 Figure 5. Reconstructed bony labyrinths of the holotype of *Mioeutoticus shipmani* (KNM-RU 2052). Left (pink) bony labyrinth in 1) posterior
 412 view; 2) anterior view; 3) inferior view; and 4) lateral view. Right (yellow) bony labyrinth in 5) posterior view; 6) anterior view; 7) inferior
 413 view; and 8) lateral view. Scale bar is 5mm.

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417 4. Discussion

418 The palaeoecology of *Mioeutoticus* and its relationships to modern taxa are currently mostly
 419 unexplored and remain largely untested. Given these constraints, it is important to document the
 420 anatomy of the main sensory systems and consider the evolutionary implications of the nasal,
 421 orbital, and inner ear morphologies observed in this specimen.

422

423 *Olfaction*

424 A direct comparison between several modern and extinct lorid olfactory systems, as well as that of
 425 the fossil prosimian *Rooneyia*, analysed in Lundeen & Kirk (2019) and Lundeen (2020) is undertaken
 426 here to highlight the most prominent and remarkable characteristics of the reconstructed
 427 *Mioeutoticus* turbinals. The turbinals are described and compared from the relative posterior to
 428 anterior position in the olfactory system.

429 *Nycticebus*

430 The MT/mt sits almost directly under the other turbinals in the olfactory system of *Nycticebus*,
 431 whereas in *Mioeutoticus*, the rest of the turbinal assemblage is posterior to the MT/mt. This is a
 432 particularly disparate feature when comparing ET/et-I, which is in a significantly more posterior
 433 relative position to MT/mt in *Mioeutoticus*; more posterior than even the NT/nt. The FT/ft are similar
 434 in relative surface area, but the FT/ft of *Nycticebus* has a scrolling rather than the arc structure seen

435 in *Mioeuoticus*. Furthermore, the posterior of the FT/ft has an increasingly steep anterior slope
 436 gradient towards the anterior which is much more extreme than that seen in *Mioeuoticus*. ET/et-I is
 437 much larger in relative surface area in *Nycticebus*, and it extends much more anteriorly than that of
 438 *Mioeuoticus*, extending to the same limit as the MT/mt. The IT/it is situated consistently between
 439 ET/et-I & II in *Nycticebus*, whereas it is placed between the shared basal lamina of ET/et-I & II and
 440 ET/et-III anteriorly then moving posteriorly on the coronal plane, the ET/et-II contacts the lateral
 441 nasal wall directly and so the IT/it location shifts to between ET/et-I and ET/et-II. The IT is similar in
 442 relative surface area to the rest of the assemblage, though it has a more elongated structure in
 443 *Nycticebus* than in *Mioeuoticus*. The NT/nt is similar in relative size, position and structure in both
 444 species, but has a much steeper slope gradient on the sagittal plane in *Nycticebus*. ET/et-II & III are
 445 also strikingly similar in relative surface area, position, structure and slope gradient on the sagittal
 446 plane in both species. The most disparate characteristic in *Nycticebus* is the presence of an ET/et-IV,
 447 which is absent in *Mioeuoticus*. The MT/mt are much more anterior to the rest of the turbinals in the
 448 *Mioeuoticus* olfactory system than in *Nycticebus*. The *Nycticebus* specimen from Lundeen & Kirk
 449 (2019), MCZ-BOM-5118, has a much smaller OTSA of 691.47mm² in comparison to 1184mm² in
 450 *Mioeuoticus*, but a much larger MTSA of 221.74mm² as opposed to 151.36mm².

451 *Loris*

452 NT/nt has a slightly steeper slope gradient on the sagittal plane in the olfactory system of *Loris* than
 453 in that of *Mioeuoticus*, and this turbinal is not scrolled towards the posterior in the modern
 454 counterpart. Comparatively, the MT/mt in *Mioeuoticus* is proportionally much greater in length than
 455 the other turbinals in the assemblage. The FT/ft sits superomedially to the NT/nt in *Loris*, as opposed
 456 to the lateral position seen in *Mioeuoticus*. The turbinals overlay one another considerably more in
 457 the *Loris* olfactory system, which as a result is much more compact than in *Mioeuoticus*. The NT/nt,
 458 ET/et-I, II & III are all much greater in relative surface area and length than in *Mioeuoticus*, though
 459 these turbinals remain similar in relative size in each species. These turbinals all also have more
 460 scrolled structures than those of *Mioeuoticus*, though it is difficult to determine if this is because of
 461 breakage in the latter. ET/et-I & II converge in the *Loris* olfactory system, and the lateral edge of ET-II
 462 extends much further to the posterior of the assemblage; neither of these characteristics are seen in
 463 *Mioeuoticus*. The IT/it of the olfactory system in *Loris* is similar in relative position to that of
 464 *Nycticebus*, but it has a more comparable relative length to the IT/it in *Mioeuoticus*, though it is
 465 much larger in relative surface area. Contrastingly to *Mioeuoticus*, *Loris* has an ET-IV, which is much
 466 greater in relative size than that of *Nycticebus*. The *Loris* specimen from Lundeen & Kirk (2019), BAA-
 467 0006, has a much smaller OTSA with 713.62mm² in comparison to 1184mm² in *Mioeuoticus*, but the
 468 MTSA is much larger at 221.20mm² as opposed to 151.36mm².

469 *Perodicticus*

470 *Perodicticus* has a comparatively much larger NT/nt than that seen in *Mioeuoticus*. The NT/nt in the
 471 modern counterpart is greater in relative length, surface area and volume than the rest of the
 472 assemblage, comparable to that of the MT/mt. The NT also has a much steeper slope gradient on the
 473 sagittal plane in *Perodicticus* than in *Mioeuoticus*, and it is much more complex in structure,
 474 extending medially until ventral to the FT/ft. The IT/it between ET/et-II & III in *Perodicticus* bears
 475 similarity to the posterior arrangement in *Mioeuoticus*. Opposingly to the overall arrangement of the
 476 *Mioeuoticus* turbinal assemblage, the *Perodicticus* has a 'compact' overlaid arrangement like that
 477 of *Nycticebus*. In further contrast to *Mioeuoticus*, the ET/et-I & I are fused – like *Nycticebus* – and the
 478 ET/ET-II is much smaller in proportion to ET/et-I. The IT/it, ET/et-II & III are in a similar relative
 479 position in the overall assemblage, as seen in *Mioeuoticus*. The MT/mt are broadly similar in relative
 480 surface area and shape but the *Mioeuoticus* turbinals are too fractured to make a more distinct

481 comparison. As seen in the previous modern species analysed here, *Perodicticus* has an ET/et-IV,
 482 notably absent in *Mioeuoticus*. The *Perodicticus* specimen in Lundeen & Kirk (2019), MCZ-25831, is
 483 similar in OTSA with 1258.80mm² in comparison to 1184mm² in *Mioeuoticus*, especially when
 484 considering the latter is considerably more fragmented; the MTSA is considerably higher in
 485 *Perodicticus*, however, with 366.35mm² as opposed to 151.36mm².

486 *Arctocebus*

487 From the rostral to caudal limits of the *Arctocebus* turbinal assemblage, the NT/nt has a similar
 488 relative surface area, position, scrolled structure and slope gradient to that seen in *Mioeuoticus*. The
 489 *Arctocebus* NT/nt has a strong contrasting feature, however, in that an anterior portion of the
 490 turbinal extends laterally towards the inferoventral and then diverges posteriorly below the anterior
 491 edge of the FT/ft. The NT/nt also has a similar posterior position relative to the MT/mt, a feature also
 492 seen in *Mioeuoticus*. Opposingly, the ET/et-I below extends much more anteriorly in a similar
 493 position to that of the MT/mt in *Nycticebus*, *Loris* and *Perodicticus*. ET/et-I & II are fused – alike to
 494 that of *Perodicticus*, but in contrast to *Mioeuoticus*. The ET/et-II is a much more tightly scrolled
 495 structure, and longer in relative length, in *Arctocebus* than in *Mioeuoticus*. The slope gradient on the
 496 sagittal plane is also much shallower in *Arctocebus* and it does not increase towards the posterior as
 497 it does in *Mioeuoticus*. IT/it between ET/et-II & III which bears similarity to the posterior arrangement
 498 in *Mioeuoticus*. The ET/et-III is similar in relative surface area, structure and position to that seen in
 499 *Mioeuoticus*. As in the comparative specimens above, *Arctocebus* has an ET/et-IV, which is absent in
 500 *Mioeuoticus*. The *Perodicticus* specimen in Lundeen & Kirk (2019) is similar in OTSA with
 501 1258.80mm² compared to 1184mm² in *Mioeuoticus*, especially when considering the latter is
 502 considerably more fragmented; the MTSA is considerably higher in *Perodicticus*, however, with
 503 366.35mm² as opposed to 151.36mm².

504 *Rooneyia*

505 In several respects, there is a close similarity in the organization of the nasal turbinals in *Mioeuoticus*
 506 and *Rooneyia* (Lundeen & Kirk, 2009). The posterior of the NT/nt in both specimens are connected to
 507 the superior wall of the nasal fossa via only the superior-most basal lamina. The central portion of
 508 both NT/nt take the form of a mediolaterally compressed scroll and the posterior-most of the NT/nt
 509 are more restricted in cross-sectional area and positioned in the superior nasal cavity, above the
 510 ET/et I and superomedial to the FT/ft. The NT/nt of *Rooneyia* contrasts in that an anterior portion of
 511 the turbinal extends laterally towards the inferoventral and then diverges posteriorly just
 512 anterolateral to the MT/mt. The FT/ft in *Mioeuoticus* and *Rooneyia* have a strikingly similar arcuate
 513 structure with an anteriorly sloping gradient that mirrors the NT/nt. In both species, the anterior
 514 margin of ET/et I forms a mediolaterally compressed and inferolaterally directed enclosed bulla
 515 which increases in volume and opens to a scroll structure anteriorly. The IT/it between ET/et I & II in
 516 *Perodicticus* bears similarity to the anterior arrangement in *Mioeuoticus*. The ET/et II turbinal in both
 517 species is inferomedial to ET/et I, orientated anteromedially in the olfactory cavity with a steep
 518 anterior gradient on the sagittal plane. Anteriorly, the ET/et of both *Mioeuoticus* and *Rooneyia* are
 519 branching structures contacting the superior and lateral fossa wall, then the connection with the
 520 superior fossa wall is lost as the structure modifies to the main portion of this turbinal, a singular
 521 bulla. Although the ET/et II is closely associated with ET/et I in *Mioeuoticus* and *Rooneyia*, ET/et II
 522 does not contact any other adjacent turbinals in either assemblage. It is difficult to discern whether
 523 the ET/et *Mioeuoticus* is bullar, like that of *Rooneyia*, or arched towards the anterior as this is not
 524 clear on the CT rendering. The visible structure does seem to follow the same general structure.
 525 Posteriorly, this arcuate turbinal curves more steeply to form a single medial scroll with branches
 526 that contact the lateral and cribriform walls in both species. *Mioeuoticus* lacks an ET/et-IV evident in

527 the *Rooneyia* turbinal assemblage and has a much larger OTSA relative to body size. The *Rooneyia*
 528 specimen in Lundeen (2020) has an OTSE of only 408.31mm² compared to 1184mm² in *Mioeuoticus*,
 529 and a much lower MTSA of 145.42mm² as opposed to 151.36mm².

530 *Mioeuoticus*

531 When comparing the total olfactory turbinal surface area relative to the cranial size of *Mioeuoticus*
 532 with that of extant and extinct primates in Lundeen & Kirk's (2019) study, it is evident that
 533 *Mioeuoticus* has an olfactory turbinal surface area that is broadly similar to similar-sized
 534 strepsirrhines *Propithecus verreauxi*, *Euoticus elegantulus* and *Perodicticus potto* (Figure 6). The
 535 surface area of *Mioeuoticus* is slightly smaller and plots just below the lower limit of strepsirrhine
 536 distribution. However, this is certainly due to underestimation in our research due to fragmentation
 537 and breakage. Particularly as *Mioeuoticus* has a notably extended olfactory recess length (7.53mm).
 538 A large olfactory recess has been considered characteristic of mammals with a well-developed sense
 539 of smell (Craven et al. 2010) and haplorrhines are reported to have an absence of an olfactory recess
 540 (Smith and Rossie, 2008; Smith et al., 2014).

541

542

543 Figure 6. Biplot showing log-transformed olfactory turbinal surface area and log-transformed skull geometric mean. Taxon abbreviations: Al = *Alouatta*; Ao = *Aotus*; At = *Ateles*; Av = *Avahi*; Ca = *Plecturocebus*; Ct = *Carlito*; Cx = *Callithrix*; Cv = *Cynocephalus*; Da = *Daubentonia*; Ee =
 544 *Euoticus*; Eu = *Eulemur*; Gm = *Galago moholi*; Gs = *Galago senegalensis*; Ga = *Galeopterus*; Ha = *Hapalemur*; Hy = *Hylobates*; In = *Indri*; Lm = *Lepilemur*; Lo = *Loris*; Ma = *Mandrillus*; Mo = *Mioeuoticus*; Mz = *Mirza*; Mi = *Miopithecus*; Ny = *Nycticebus*; Ot = *Otolemur*; Pe =
 545 *Perodicticus*; Ph = *Presbytis*; Pr = *Ptilocolobus*; Pv = *Propithecus*; Pt = *Ptilocercus*; Rv = *Rooneyia*; Sa = *Saimiri*; Tb = *Tupaia belangeri*; Tg =
 546 *Tupaia glis*; and Va = *Varecia*.

549 The most striking feature in the *Mioeuoticus* olfactory system is the location of the interturbinal. In
550 lemuriforms, ET/et-II originates from ET/et-I and/or the horizontal lamina and so the interturbinal is
551 located between the shared basal lamina of ET/et-I & II or horizontal lamina and ET/et-III, whereas in
552 loriforms, ET/et-II contacts the lateral nasal wall directly and so the interturbinal is located between
553 ET/et-II and ET/et-III (Lundeen & Kirk, 2009). The interturbinal of *Mioeuoticus* is unique in that,
554 anteriorly, it is located between the shared basal lamina of ET/et-I & II and ET/et-III, as seen in
555 lemuriforms. However, moving posteriorly on the coronal plane, ET/et-II contacts the lateral nasal
556 wall directly and so the interturbinal location changes. Notably, this is not between ET/et-II and
557 ET/et-III but instead between ET/et-I and ET/et-II, so not the exact point of contact seen in modern
558 loriforms. This turbinal arrangement is not seen in any strepsirrhine and the shared turbinal
559 morphology with lemuriforms likely denotes the primitive status of *Mioeuoticus* within Lorisidae,
560 consistent with the idea that it might be a stem member of the family (Harrison, 2010).

561 *Audition*

562 Despite some features being indeterminable in the *Mioeuoticus* inner ear reconstruction, there are
563 still key anatomical characteristics that give insights into the auditory capabilities and locomotor
564 agility of the specimen, and thus phylogenetic status of the species.

565 The fusion of the anterior and posterior semicircular canals seen in the *Mioeuoticus* holotype is a
566 common characteristic in numerous extant and extinct primates (Benoit et al. 2013), and the
567 orthogonality between this structure and the plane of the lateral semi-circular canal is a condition
568 that can also be observed in several primates, including Lorisidae (Lebrun et al., 2012). The oval
569 lateral canals and short common crura of the specimen are commonly exhibited by Loriformes, as
570 opposed to the rounded lateral canals and long common crura which are indicative of Lemuriformes
571 (Lebrun, 2010). The *Mioeuoticus* cochlea is broad and bulky, similar in morphology to that seen in
572 modern *Loris* (Figure 7i, A-H) though significantly larger than *Nycticebus* and *Perodicticus* (Figure 7ii,
573 A-H). The common crura is short relative to the cochlea and semi-circular canals, with a narrow utricle
574 and vestibule, similar to that seen in *Nycticebus* (Figure 7iii, A-H). The strong ovate shape of the semi-
575 circular canals is comparable between *Perodicticus* and *Mioeuoticus*, though the relative size
576 between the canals is morphologically closer to that of *Nycticebus* (Figure 7iv, A-H).

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578 Figure 7. Digital visualisations of the (i) Reconstructed left (pink) bony labyrinths of extant *Loris lydekkerianus* in A) anterolateral view, B)
 579 lateral view, C) posterolateral view, and D) dorsal view; Reconstructed right (green) bony labyrinths of extant *Loris lydekkerianus* in E)
 580 anterolateral view, F) lateral view, G) posterolateral view, and H) dorsal view; (ii) Reconstructed left (pink) bony labyrinths of extant
 581 *Nycticebus bengalensis* in A) anterolateral view, B) lateral view, C) posterolateral view, and D) dorsal view; ii) Reconstructed right (green)
 582 bony labyrinths of extant *Nycticebus bengalensis* in E) anterolateral view, F) lateral view, G) posterolateral view, and H) dorsal view; iii) (i)
 583 Reconstructed left (pink) bony labyrinths of extant *Perodicticus potto* in A) anterolateral view, B) lateral view, C) posterolateral view, and D)
 584 dorsal view; ii) Reconstructed right (green) bony labyrinths of extant *Perodicticus potto* in E) anterolateral view, F) lateral view, G)
 585 posterolateral view, and H) dorsal view; iv) (i) Reconstructed left (pink) bony labyrinths of *Mioeuoticus* holotype (KNM-RU 2052) in A)
 586 anterolateral view, B) lateral view, C) posterolateral view, and D) dorsal view; ii) Reconstructed right (green) bony labyrinths of *Mioeuoticus*
 587 in E) anterolateral view, F) lateral view, G) posterolateral view, and H) dorsal view. Scale bar is 10mm.

588 The 105° angle between the anterior and posterior semicircular canals in the *Mioeuoticus* specimen
 589 is remarkably consistent with the angles between the arcs at the greatest width of the anterior and
 590 posterior semicircular canals on the transverse plane (AScM < PScM) of platyrrhine and catarrhine
 591 anthropoids reported by Spoor and Zonneveld (1998). According to this study, most primates exhibit
 592 an AScM < PScM much greater than 90°, and the platyrrhine and catarrhine anthropoids have an
 593 overlapping distribution spanning 101°–110°. Following the current models correlating canal
 594 orthogonality and locomotor agility (e.g., Malinzak et al., 2012; Berlin et al. 2013), we hypothesise
 595 that the significant deviation from orthogonality of the angles between all of the canals in the
 596 *Mioeuoticus* inner ear reconstruction may indicate slower rotational head speeds and a lower mean
 597 vestibular sensitivity to motion.

598 Unfortunately, the fragmented nature of the ear canal reconstructions means that it is not possible
 599 to measure the curvature radii in this specimen to definitively correlate canal radius of curvature and
 600 agility level to reconstruct locomotor behaviours (e.g., Spoor et al., 2007, Silcox et al., 2009, Ryan et
 601 al., 2012). We can, however, make a more general observation in this regard. The lateral canal has
 602 the shortest radius of the bony labyrinth in *Mioeuoticus*, and this characteristic is considered to be
 603 diagnostic of less agile behaviours (Walker et al., 2008; Spoor et al., 2009).

604 The data in this auditory analysis of the *Mioeuoticus* holotype must be considered with caution, as
 605 several publications have determined that it is difficult to predict and differentiate vestibular
 606 sensitivities of slower-moving species from faster-moving ones when only a single specimen is
 607 available, as the morphologies of various individuals within a species and across several species
 608 overlap considerably (e.g., Perier et al., 2016; Bernardi and Couette., 2017; Bhagat et al., 2021).
 609 Recent studies indicate that the results acquired from measuring the orthogonality of the
 610 semicircular canals in any organism can induce a fair amount of variability, particularly in a slow-
 611 moving taxon (e.g., Gonzales et al. 2019). To make a more ascertained hypothesis here, future
 612 studies would be required to determine the patterns of interspecific variation across a broad sample
 613 of primates to better understand the resolution at which locomotion can be reconstructed from
 614 single individuals.

615

616 *Vision*

617 When making direct comparisons with the extant primate daOFQ and nsOFQ's from Kirk & Kay
 618 (2004), the *Mioeuoticus* specimen has OFQs that fall well below the range of OFQs for extant diurnal
 619 and nocturnal haplorhines, just within the lowest range of OFQs for extant diurnal strepsirrhine (the
 620 lowest daOFQ being 56.9 for *Hapalemur griseus*) and well within the range of OFQs for extant
 621 nocturnal strepsirrhines. The most similar OFQ values from the extant primates analysed in Kirk &
 622 Kay (2004) are the diurnal strepsirrhine *Hapalemur griseus* (daOFQ = 56.9, nsOFQ = 16.40, the
 623 nocturnal strepsirrhines *Galago matschiei* (daOFQ = 57.1, nsOFQ = 15.2) and *Perodicticus potto*
 624 (daOFQ = 57.2, nsOFQ = 15.5).

625 The OFQ value calculated for any given primate acts as a proxy for the degree of retinal summation,
626 which is a quantification of the number of photoreceptor cells that converge on bipolar cells in the
627 eye to transmit signals to ganglion cells for transfer to the brain for interpretation and response (Kay
628 & Kirk, 2000). Thus, OFQ gives a direct indication as to the degree of visual acuity in a primate; low
629 OFQ means high central retinal summation and high OFQ means low central retinal summation (Kirk
630 & Kay, 2004).

631 *Mioeuoticus* is known to be a Strepsirrhine lorised (Seiffert et al. 2007; Harrison et al. 2010; López-
632 Torres & Silcox, 2020), and the OFQs calculated here have broadly low values which indicates a high
633 central retinal summation, comparable to extant strepsirrhines with a nocturnal activity pattern.
634 Thus, it is probable that *Mioeuoticus* had central retinas with a large proportion of high summation
635 rods which increased sensitivity to light at the expense of visual acuity - an adaptation to low light
636 levels.

637 The similarity in OFQs seen between this specimen, *Perodicticus potto* and *Hapalemur griseus* could
638 suggest that these extant nocturnal strepsirrhines have retained a primitive optic morphology, and
639 thus nocturnal vision, as a generally plesiomorphic character state inherited from the ancestral
640 *Mioeuoticus*. Accordingly, it may be surmised that the visual acuity and optic morphology of these
641 extant descendants may closely resemble this ancestral state character.

642

643 **Conclusion**

644 Our research provides a unique new understanding of *Mioeuoticus*' behaviours and how the sensory
645 sensitivities in this fossil lorised compare to extant loriseds. Computed tomographic (CT) analyses of
646 the sensory systems visible in the *Mioeuoticus* holotype specimen suggest it had a keen olfactory
647 sense, less agile locomotion, and visual adaptations for a nocturnal lifestyle, like that of modern
648 strepsirrhines. Our data are consistent with *Mioeuoticus* being a member of the Lorisedae family but
649 unfortunately cannot classify its phyletic position as either stem or crown. We propose that future
650 research would benefit from studying *Perodicticus potto*'s primitive sensory capabilities as a 'living'
651 model for *Mioeuoticus* and other extinct nocturnal strepsirrhines.

652

653 **Author Contributions**

654 H.E.A contributed to data analysis, interpretation, and primary authorship of the manuscript. S.L.T
655 contributed to the conception of the research, data analysis, interpretation, and authorship of the
656 manuscript. M.T.S. contributed to the data interpretation in the manuscript.

657

658 **Competing Interest Statement**

659 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships
660 that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

661

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